

EFFECTIVE USE OF ELLIPSIS IN ENGLISH ADVERTISING

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Abstract: This article is devoted to investigate the extent to which the conventions of the English language are broken in advertising. There are also shown the practical usage of lexical-semantic features in this paper. This article is based on several obvious examples which strengthen the theoretical part of it.

Key words: ellipsis, syntactic form, antecedent, phrase ellipsis, stylistic device, Computational Linguistics, elliptical constructions.

Ellipsis is a term used in grammatical analysis to refer to a sentence where a part of the structure has been omitted. The reasons of implication of elliptical constructions in a certain language can be economy, emphasis of an individual part of a sentence and the matter of style [1].

Ellipsis seems to be able to overshadow the basic question of form-meaning correspondence and the usual mechanism of grasping a meaning out of its form is by passed in the interpretation of elliptical constructions. The fairly different picture of mapping of ellipsis poses a direct impediment for Computational Linguistics. The latter is to show that language is a correlation of syntactic forms with meaning and there is a systematic mapping from form to meaning in human language [2].

There is observed verbal ellipsis in advertisements.

For example:

[Are you] Mates coming around? (advertisement for Heineken beer)

[Are you] Feeling fruity? (advertisement for Del Monte juice)

In this example we see the missing antecedent for the auxiliary verb “to be” and here the full meaning of the sentence is not destructed.

The second type of ellipsis is nominal ellipsis.

[It] Starts perfect... [It] Stays perfect (advertisement for Max Factor make up foundation)

The dream to [your] dream car is [your] home (advertisement for Halifax Insurance)

Based on researches it is named the antecedent for verb phrase ellipsis a proverb, that is to say a proverb is the main indicative of meaning for the elided construction. There are two operations used to interpret the preform: storing meaning and retrieving meaning. Storing meaning is identifying a meaning by its potential antecedent and the latter-selecting among the stored possible antecedents. Meanings are stored in a semantic form known as discourse model. The meaning-bearer is termed as dynamic individual and the interpretation of a proverb requires a specific selection of a dynamic individual from the discourse model (stored meaning). The selection of a proverb or an antecedent is denoted by a fixed index of the derivation but in the process of recovering meaning there is no accepted and optimal way of identifying an antecedent, exactly the same both structurally and semantically.

As it has been mentioned, elliptical constructions give the availability to understand a fuller meaning with a cut or elided sentence, and the recoverable meaning can be expressed partially contained in ellipsis either in semantic or syntactic terms. The basic issue of specialist is to examine ellipsis in both the given terms (syntactic and semantic) and to provide answers to the identity questions of ellipsis. Ellipsis is ruled by a semantic identity condition.

For example:

My mother practically told me, "You know that what you're doing is a career, right?" I said, "Is it [a career], really?"

Noun phrase ellipsis is defined when the noun and the potentially accompanying modifiers are omitted from a noun phrase. This type of ellipsis is also referred to as nominal, subject ellipsis. Although there have been theoretical attempts to explain English subject ellipsis, they have not generally described the

phenomenon in great detail. The studies of child language acquisition have revealed evidences of subject omission in child speech. The most commonly omitted subjects are considered to be “I” and “it” and their identities were recoverable from the preceding linguistic information. Sentences in English typically contain overt subjects. However subject ellipsis is not a rarity especially in conversation [3].

Sentences lacking overt subjects are interpretable and not appear to be errors on the part of speakers. For example: in a “don't know” answer to a question one does not know the answer to, we understand who is the doer of the action, although the subject “I” is amiss. Subject ellipsis has been studied within specific genres of text such as diary registers and telegraphic communiqués where economy is paramount. It is suggested, that because English speakers cannot use verbal agreement to identify ellipited subjects, they must look for antecedents in the broader context of the text, but do not make any claims about the syntactic properties of a null subject that might influence its identification. More recently S.Nariyama examined a corpus of Australian English composed of dialogues from Australian TV dramas and argued that the subject sentences in English carry different connotations than their “normal” equivalents. It is also suggested that in emails a more casual attitude is reflected towards the reader on the part of the author. As it is mentioned above, the most commonly omitted subject is “I” while there have been witnessed cases of “he, she, it”- subject ellipsis, too. Anyway, the main characteristic feature of subject ellipsis and generally ellipsis is that of recoverability.

Ellipsis entails the omission or deletion of some items of the surface text, which are recoverable in terms of relation with the text itself. Ellipsis is considered a major cohesive device, contributing to the efficiency and compactness of a text [4]. The device has found a manifold usage in headline language. A newspaper headline is a very short summary of a news report. It normally appears in large letters above the report. The main features of the grammar of headlines are the use

of a series of nouns and the use of ellipsis (leaving out words which are not necessary).

List of used literature:

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